

Compassionate Classroom Behavior as Moderator on Reciprocative Teaching Approach and Students' Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills

Annalyn C. Cabug-os

Abstract. The current study evaluates whether compassionate classroom behavior is the relationship between teachers' reciprocating teaching approach and students' technical-vocational livelihood skills. In this study, the researcher selected 350 junior high school students who were respondents and were taken from cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City Division. A random sampling technique was utilized to select the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, multiple linear regression analysis, and Structural Equation Model through Mediation Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' reciprocating teaching approach, students' technical-vocational livelihood skills, and compassionate classroom behavior in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between teachers' reciprocating teaching approach, students' technical-vocational livelihood skills, and compassionate classroom behavior in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. The Structural Equation Model through Mediation Analysis proved that compassionate classroom behavior partially mediated the relationship between teachers' reciprocating teaching approach and students' technical-vocational livelihood skills.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management 2. reciprocating teaching approach 3. technical vocational livelihood skills 4. compassionate classroom behavior

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1. Introduction

In a teaching-learning environment known as reciprocating teaching, students were given some control over their education. If they do this, they are more likely to have higher levels of internal motivation for their academic work and to appreciate the importance of achievement-related behavior. The management of classroom interaction has several components, including controlled or regulated classroom conduct, clearly stated group or individual goals, prepared topic materials, and reinforced student behavior. As a result, students will establish strong learning habits, acquire new knowledge while expanding their worldview, be able to solve complex problems, increase their self-confidence, develop flexibility, and achieve high

learning success. In an educational context, students must learn to be willing to face the challenges of an age filled with change and uncertainty. Therefore, analyzing the extent of teachers' interactive instructional ability can play an important role in understanding the technical vocational livelihood skills of the students. On this view, Erawan (2010) noted that technical vocational livelihood skills are the capacities for adaptable and constructive behavior that enable individual to successfully handle the demands and difficulties of daily life. Technical vocational livelihood skills help individuals be adaptive, engage with their environment, and encourage self-management, according to Naseri and

Babakhani (2016). As highlighted by Greco et al. (2013), technical vocational livelihood skills include the ability to manage emotions like stress, anxiety, depression, and failure as well as life skills, effective communication skills, interpersonal relationships, empathy, decision-making, problem-solving, and critical thinking. Prior research has shown that several factors influenced students' technical vocational livelihood skills. For instance, Kashlev (2013) suggested that a unique way to organize practical activity is through reciprocative education. It suggests having very clear-cut, predictable objectives. Reciprocative teaching approach as described by Reeves, (2012) The teaching strategy of integrating students in the learning process by encouraging them to contribute their own experience and knowledge into the process, while also helping to defining or organizing their learning. As noted by Kutbiddinova (2015), reciprocative teaching activities enable students to think creatively and teach them tolerance, patience, and understanding of others. Likewise, Kutbiddinova et al. (2016) mentioned that teachers' reciprocative teaching abilities aim to foster critical and reflective thinking, research, and evaluation skills that will empower students to take proactive steps to safe-

guard, improve, and speak out for the health, wellbeing, and safety of themselves and others. Moreover, Cetin-Dindar (2016) underlines that student-centered techniques used in interactive educational tactics improve students' fundamental life skills. Accordingly, reciprocative teaching strategies enhances students to interact with knowledge and each other using various tools and emphasizes on the learning

environment where learning occurs rather than instruction itself. In a interactive learning environment the teacher is to act as a facilitator and guide learners to achieve learning goals. Adding more, Kang (2016) characterized compassionate classroom behavior in the classroom as the adversarial relationship between teachers and students may also be due to teachers' tendency to define caring in warm, fuzzy terms. According to Imna and Hassan (2015), the compassionate climate reflects the type of people who compose the organization, the work processes, means of communication and the exercise of authority within the individual organization. They also recognize that it is easy to detect differences in the climate of organizations but it is difficult to name the dimensions of these differences. Compassionate climate is atmosphere in which students help, judge, reward, constrain, and find out about each other. It influences moral attitude of the individual toward work and his environment. However, reports indicated that the poor extent of technical vocational livelihood skills seem to be undermining the academic success of students in secondary school level (Naseri Babakhani, 2016). According to Kawalekar (2017), a lack of studying affects the student negatively; moreover, it leads to low grades, low self-esteem, and low sense of values. Similarly, Pitan (2013) worked on poor life and learning skills as an educational problem among university undergraduates in the contemporary time and effective management strategies. Talking things in Philippine setting, Tindowen et al. (2015) reported that students

People with poor basic life skills were not able to cope with the complexity of the subjects and challenges in daily life routines. Although earlier studies have shown a connection between reciprocating teaching strategies and students' fundamental skills, there has only been a small amount of study on junior high school-level fundamental skills. Also, the researcher has not yet come across a mediation analysis on the relationship between these variables. Therefore, there is a need for greater study in this area. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conduct-

ing a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Cluster 6 schools in Davao City City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive correlational design through mediation analysis in order to understand the role of teachers' compassionate behavior in the reciprocating teaching approach and technological vocational livelihood skills of students, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the fundamental skills of students in the Davao City City context.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while non-experimental research is a research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research simply measure variables as they naturally occur in real world. Meanwhile, mediation analysis is a statistical method used to quantify the causal sequence by which an antecedent variable causes a mediating variable that causes a dependent variable (Mackinnon, 2019). Specifically, the study focused on determining the mediating effect of teachers' compassionate classroom behavior on the relationship between reciprocative teaching approach and technical vocational livelihood

skills of students. In mediation analysis defines the

Direct, indirect, and total effects in terms of the linear regression coefficients. The total effect is defined and estimated as the c coefficient, and the direct effect is defined and estimated as the c' coefficient. The indirect effect is defined and estimated as the product of the a and b coefficients (ab) and as the difference between the c coefficient and the c' coefficient. In this study, the researcher made use of mediation analysis because it provides information about the process by which an independent variable affects a dependent variable.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were junior high school students in Cluster 6, Davao City. The 350 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller subgroups known as strata. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could

provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those bonafide enrolled junior high school students in Cluster 6 schools in Davao City, those who do not have back subjects or failing grades, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the students' socio-economic status.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—Two sets of instruments were used in this study. A panel of experts subjected these questionnaires to content validity and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The experts' comments,

and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires. The first part of the instrument is concerned with the teachers' reciprocative teaching approach, which consists of three domains: teaching engagement, interaction, and feedback. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Cronbach's alpha value of 0.964. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale to list the items they had made. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers' receptor active teaching approach, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

Range of Mean Descriptions and Interpretations

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The reciprocative teaching approach of teachers is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	Teachers' reciprocative teaching approach is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teachers' reciprocative teaching approach is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The reciprocative teaching approach of teachers is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not extensive	The reciprocative teaching approach of teachers is never observed.

The second tool is about the technical vocational livelihood skills of students in Cluster 6, Davao City. This questionnaire was divided into indicators, namely: critical thinking, creative thinking, self-awareness, interpersonal relationship and communication skills, and decision-making and problem-solving skills. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Cron-

bach's alpha value of 0.952. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of the students' technical vocational livelihood skills, the researcher used a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

The third part of the instrument was about teachers' compassionate classroom behavior of students. The reliability of the new scale ob-

tained an overall Chronbach's alpha value is 0.958. The items the respondents answered in the questionnaire used the 5-Likert scale. The

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The technical vocational livelihood skills of students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The technical vocational livelihood skills of students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The technical vocational livelihood skills of students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The technical vocational livelihood skills of students is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not extensive	The technical vocational livelihood skills of students is never manifested.

researcher used a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations, as presented below, to determine the extent of teachers' compassionate classroom behavior.

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The compassionate classroom behavior of teachers is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The compassionate classroom behavior of teachers is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The compassionate classroom behavior of teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The compassionate classroom behavior of teachers is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not extensive	The compassionate classroom behavior of teachers is never evident.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. 1. **Permission to Conduct the Study.** The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial

Colleges, Inc., Davao City was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the

school principals of the selected public secondary schools in the Cluster 6 schools in the Division of Davao City. 2. **Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire.** After the approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The researcher conducted the survey simultaneously to administer the questionnaire. The study respondents were

given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. 3. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the data

retrieval of the questionnaire, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After this, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Data Analysis—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' compassionate classroom behavior, reciprocative teaching approach, and technical vocational livelihood skills of Cluster 6, Davao City students. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship among independent (reciprocative teaching approach), dependent (technical vocational livelihood skills of students), and mediating (teachers' compassionate

classroom behavior) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 4. Structural Equation Modelling Through Mediation Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the mediating effect of the mediating variable (teachers' compassionate classroom behavior) on the relationship between the independent (reciprocative teaching approach) variable and the dependent (technical vocational livelihood skills of students) variable. This was used to supply the answer for objective 5.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers' reciprocative teaching approach, students' technical-vocational livelihood skills, and teachers' compassionate classroom behavior in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City; the significant relationship among these variables; and the mediating effect of compassionate classroom behavior on the relationship between reciprocative teaching approach and students' technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City.

Table 1 shows the summary of the teachers' reciprocative teaching approach in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City as perceived by the junior high school students. It shows that the overall mean of the reciprocative teaching approach is 3.81, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. More so, teachers' reciprocative teach-

ing approach in terms of teaching engagement acquired the highest mean score of 3.88 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while, teachers' reciprocative teaching approach in terms of interaction got the lowest mean score of 3.75 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the public junior high school students.

The extensive rating on teachers' reciprocative teaching approach in cluster 6 public secondary schools means that the teaching practice involving learners in the educational process

by encouraging them to bring their own experience and knowledge into the process, while also contributing to defining or organizing their learning is oftentimes observed by the junior

Table 1. Summary of Teachers’ Reciprocatve Teaching Approach in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Teaching Engagement	3.88	Extensive
Interaction	3.75	Extensive
Feedback	3.79	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.81	Extensive

high school students. This supports the proposition of Reutova (2015) that reciprocative teaching approach is to increase students’ interest in the learning process and turn them into active participants in the classes. Adding more, this supports the idea of Khanin (2015) that with a reciprocative teaching approach, students learn in a new way because they are actively involved in the learning process by taking part in activities, games, conversations, solving puzzles, storytelling, and other activities.

Lastly As shown in the Table 2 is the summary on students’ technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, students’ technical vocational livelihood skills in clus-

ter 6 public secondary schools in Davao City obtained an overall mean score of 3.52 with a descriptive rating of extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the students. Adding more, results on Table 10 show that students’ technical vocational livelihood skills in terms of self-awareness acquired the highest mean score of 3.86 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, students’ technical vocational livelihood skills in terms of creative thinking acquired the lowest mean score of 3.33 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the students in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City.

Table 2. Summary of Students’ Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Critical Thinking	3.48	Extensive
Creative Thinking	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Self-Awareness	3.86	Extensive
Interpersonal Relationship and Communication Skills	3.43	Extensive
Decision-Making and Problem-Solving Skills	3.49	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.52	Extensive

The extensive rating on students' technical vocational livelihood skills means that the abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life is oftentimes manifested by junior high school students. This supports the assertion of Prasad (2018) that interpersonal and psychosocial abilities help people make wise decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate clearly, form positive relationships, relate to others, and learn to manage their lives in a healthy and advantageous way. Adding more, this is congruent to the findings of Roodbari et al. (2016) who viewed technical-vocational livelihood skills as an aptitude that combines knowledge, attitude, and skills in managing external problems in the current social situation as well as readiness for future self-adjustment. According to Heckman et al. (2015), self-management is an important skill, including managing with feelings, emotions, stress and resisting peer and family pressure.

Teachers' Compassionate Classroom Behavior in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Results in Table 3 show that teachers' compassionate classroom behavior in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City reflects an extensive category mean of 3.61, which means that it is oftentimes manifested. Notably, the

Significant Relationship among Teachers' Reciprocative Teaching Approach, Students' Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills, and Teachers' Compassionate Classroom Behavior in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

The results of the analysis of the relationship among teachers' reciprocative teaching approach, students' technical vocational livelihood skills, and compassionate classroom behavior are presented. Bivariate correlation

mean ratings of the different items range from 2.88 to 4.29. The table further reveals that the item Cooperating with students when doing assigned work has a mean rating of 2.88, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes evident in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. Meanwhile, the item Caring about the feelings of the students reflects a mean rating of 4.29, described as very extensive and interpreted as compassionate classroom behavior of teachers, which is always evident in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. This implies that the ability to maintain adversarial relationships between teachers and students is oftentimes evident in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. This supports the idea of Imna and Hassan (2015) that a compassionate climate reflects the type of people who compose the organization, the work processes, means of communication, and the exercise of authority within the individual organization. Adding more, this supports the findings of Zhu et al. (2013) that learning institution where teachers addressed the different needs and characteristics of students, the students were able to reveal their creativity in learning processes. Likewise, this agrees with the view of Eade (2011) that compassionate classroom behavior is necessary for improved student learning and that the teaching profession requires pedagogy including innovation.

analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned. Table 4 shows that teachers' reciprocative teaching approach has a significant positive relationship with the students' technical-vocational livelihood skills with a p-value of .000 which is less than a .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .953$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the teachers' reciprocative teaching approach changes, students' technical vocational liveli-

Table 3. Teachers' Compassionate Classroom Behavior in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Making friends with the students in the class	3.29	Moderately Extensive
2. Building personal connections among students in the class	3.19	Moderately Extensive
3. Helping students understand their work	3.99	Extensive
4. Cooperating with students when doing assigned work	2.88	Moderately Extensive
5. Sharing books, materials, and supplies with the students	3.38	Moderately Extensive
6. Caring about the feelings of the students	4.29	Very Extensive
7. Helping students when they have trouble with their work	3.88	Extensive
8. Talking to students	3.14	Moderately Extensive
9. Interacting with students on class activities	4.07	Extensive
10. Working with students in order for them to achieve class goals	4.02	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.61	Extensive

hood skills also significantly change. This supports Savas and Gurel's (2014) proposition that teachers who were able to organize learning environments effectively were able to manage their classrooms better and positively affect stu-

dent achievement and behaviors. Likewise, this supports Tomlinson and Jarvis' (2014) idea that reciprocal teaching strategies eliminate students' disruptive behavior.

On one hand, the result shows that the relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach and compassionate classroom behavior in the cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City has a significant positive strong relationship with a p-value of .00 that is less than the alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.972$ p ; 0.05). This means that if the extent of teachers' reciprocal teaching approach changes, the extent of compassionate classroom behavior also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach and compassionate classroom behavior in clus-

ter 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. This supports Yu's (2014) assertion that the reciprocal approach helps engage students in real-world tasks rather than multiple-choice tests and evaluates them according to criteria that are important for actual performance in a field of work. According to Blazar (2016), managing the behavior of students in the classroom affects instruction, learning, and performance. On the other hand, the result shows that the relationship between teachers' compassionate classroom behavior has a significant positive relationship with the student's technical vocational livelihood skills has a significant positive

Table 4. Significant Relationship among Teachers’ Reciprocal Teaching Approach, Students’ Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills, and Teachers’ Compassionate Classroom Behavior in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Variables	Students’ Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills	Compassionate Classroom Behavior
Reciprocal Teaching Approach	0.953** (0.000)	0.972** (0.000)
Students’ Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills	1	0.974** (0.000)

**Significant @ $p < 0.05$

strong relationship with a p-value of .00 that is less than the alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.974$, $p < .05$). This means that if the extent of teachers’ compassionate classroom behavior changes, students’ technical vocational livelihood skills also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers’ compassionate classroom behavior and a significant positive relationship with the students’ technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. This result agrees with Cirik’s et al. (2013) idea that in a compassionate learning environment, the assessment of student learning is interwoven with teaching and occurs through teacher observations of students at work and through exhibitions and portfolios. In this classroom setting, the prospective teachers are trained to design and implement learning activities that promote learners’ reflective and creative thinking, communication, and collaboration skills and serve their diverse learning needs.

The Mediating Effect of Compassionate

Classroom Behavior on the Relationship Between Teachers’ Reciprocal Teaching Approach and Students’ Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

The mediating effect of compassionate classroom behavior on the relationship between teachers’ reciprocal teaching approach and students’ technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 public secondary schools was tested on JASP software using the Structural equation model through mediation analysis. Results in Table 13 show that the total effect of teachers’ reciprocal teaching approach (RTA) as the independent variable on the work performance, which is this study’s dependent variable is significant, is significant as evident in the estimated value of 0.963 and $p < 0.05$. On one hand, it could be seen in the table that the direct effect of teachers’ reciprocal teaching approach (RTA) on the students’ technical vocational livelihood skills (TVLS), was significant as indicated by an estimated value of 0.124, $p < 0.05$. Lastly, teachers’ reciprocal teaching approach (RTA)

on the students' technical vocational livelihood skills (TVLS) with compassionate classroom behavior (CCB) as a mediator, is significant as indicated by the estimated value of 0.839 and $p < 0.05$. Therefore, it could be said that partial mediation took place.

Thus, the null hypothesis of compassionate classroom behavior (CCB) does not mediate the relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach (RTA) and students' technical vocational Livelihood skills (TVLS) in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City is rejected. The table also indicates the results of the computation of the effect size in

the mediation test conducted between the three variables. The effect size measures how much of the effect of teachers' reciprocal teaching approach (RTA) on the students' technical vocational livelihood skills (TVLS) can be attributed to the indirect path. As shown in the figure, the ratio index obtains a value of 0.871, indicating that about 87.10 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 12.90 percent of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

Table 5. The Mediating Effect of Compassionate Classroom Behavior on the Relationship Between Teachers' Reciprocal Teaching Approach and Students' Technical Vocational Livelihood Skills in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Effect Type	Path	Estimate	Std. Error	p-value
Indirect Effect Components	RTA → CCB → TVLS	0.839	0.052	16.281 (0.000)
Direct Effect	RTA → TVLS	0.124	0.052	2.390 (0.000)
Total Effect	RTA → TVLS	0.963	0.016	58.786 (0.000)
Ratio Index = 0.871				
Legend: RTA=Reciprocal Teaching Approach; TVLS=Students' Technical Vocational Skills; CCB=Compassionate Classroom Behavior				

Through mediation analysis, the mediation model shown in Figure 2 was generated. The significant role of compassionate classroom behavior (CCB) as a mediator in the relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach (RTA) and students' technical vocational livelihood skills (TVLS) is contributed by the fact that there exists a relationship among these variables. It is emphasized in this study that compassionate classroom behavior (CCB) is an

undeniable factor that has a positive relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach (RTA) and students' technical vocational livelihood skills (TVLS) in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The significant mediating effect of compassionate classroom behavior on the relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach and students' technical vocational skills supports Kashlev's (2013) idea that interactive learning is a unique way to

organize cognitive activity. Accordingly, the reciprocative teaching approach encourages students to interact with knowledge and one another using various technologies and places more emphasis on the learning environment than on the actual lesson. Lastly, the Teacher Thoughts and Action Process Model by Peterson and Clark (1970) posits that the individual thought process occurs inside the brain and

cannot be measured directly. The thought process includes engaging thoughts and decision-making, the belief system and the associated theories built around it, and the overall planning part, including the three stages of pre-, post-, and interactive thoughts. It can also categorize teachers according to these three stages as teachers distinguish themselves in their thought processes.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusion and recommendation. The literature supports the discussion in the first chapters, and the conclusion was made up of statements about the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to determine the mediating effect of compassionate classroom behavior on the relationship between teachers' reciprocative teaching approach and students' technical-vocational livelihood skills utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using structural equation modeling through mediation analysis. The researcher selected the 350 junior high school students in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City as the respondents through a random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following:

The extent of teachers' reciprocative teaching approach in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.81 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, teachers' reciprocative teaching approach in

In terms of teaching engagement, interaction, and feedback, the mean scores were 3.88, 3.75, and 3.79, respectively. The extent of students' technical-vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City

has an overall mean of 3.52 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, students' technical-vocational livelihood skills in critical thinking, creative thinking, self-awareness, interpersonal relationship and communication skills, and decision-making and problem-solving skills obtained mean scores of 3.48, 3.83, 3.86, 3.43, and 3.49, respectively. Moreover, the extent of teachers' compassionate classroom behavior has an overall mean of 3.61 with a descriptive rating of extensive. The result showed that teachers' reciprocative teaching approach has a significant positive relationship with the student's technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .953$, $p < 0.05$). On the one hand, teachers' reciprocative teaching approach has a significant positive relationship with compassionate classroom behavior with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .972$, $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, teachers' compassionate classroom behavior has a significant positive relationship with the student's technical-vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of sig-

nificance (two-tailed) ($r = .974, p < 0.05$). Compassionate classroom behavior mediates the relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach and students' technical-vocational livelihood skills.

in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City. The analysis obtained the estimates value of 0.839 with $p < 0.05$, 0.124 with $p < 0.05$, and 0.963 with $p < 0.05$ for indirect, direct, and total effects, respectively. Moreover, the ratio index obtains a value of 0.871, indicating that about 87.10 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 12.90 percent of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as the survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions were generated: Teachers' reciprocal teaching approach in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City was described as extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' reciprocal teaching approach regarding teaching engagement, interaction, and feedback belongs to extensive rating. This means that junior high school students often observe the teaching practice of involving learners in the educational process by encouraging them to bring their own experience and knowledge into the process while also contributing to defining or organizing their learning. These students' technical-vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City acquired extensive ratings. Meanwhile, students' technical-vocational livelihood skills in terms of critical thinking, creative thinking, self-awareness, interpersonal relationship and communication skills, and decision-making and problem-solving skills belong to extensive ratings.

This means that junior high school students oftentimes manifest the abilities for adaptive

and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. The compassionate classroom behavior of the teachers in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City acquired an extensive rating. This implies that the ability to maintain adversarial relationships between teachers and students is often evident in these schools. Teachers' reciprocal teaching approach has a positive significant relationship with students' technical vocational livelihood skills and compassionate classroom behavior of the teachers in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City. Also, compassionate classroom behavior has a positive significant relationship with students' technical-vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City. Compassionate classroom behavior significantly mediates the relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach and students' technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 secondary public schools in Davao City. It is emphasized in this study that compassionate classroom behavior is an undeniable factor that has a positive relationship between teachers' reciprocal teaching approach and students' technical vocational livelihood skills in cluster 6 public secondary schools in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—The researcher recommends that school administrators may endeavor to provide public elementary teachers with orientation that might give the teachers adequate background and knowledge and usable information to know how to apply culturally responsive tools and strategies. Building background knowledge was essential in becoming aware of the dimensions of culture and the larger social, political, and economic conditions that create inequitable education outcomes. The researcher may recommend that DepEd officials formulate policies to improve educational practices related to students' technical vocational livelihood skills. This policy would create qual-

ity standards for learning and teaching and set expectations and accountability. Further, teachers may have developed interventions that can be implemented regarding the importance of analyzing teachers' reciprocative teaching approach and compassionate classroom behavior that can be very helpful to the student's technical vocational livelihood skills to achieve academically by aiding them in becoming more focused and attentive learners. Furthermore, junior high school students may have developed their technical vocational livelihood skills. These skills would help them increase their capabilities and strength and enhance the effectiveness of the learning experience. They would also guide them to plan or modify their learning methods in parallel with the students' technical vocational livelihood skills. Lastly, researchers may conduct further analysis on the factor that may contribute to the relationship between teachers' reciprocative teaching approach and students' technical vocational livelihood skills since only 77.00 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable.

5. References

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